

1 Cite this article as:

2 G. Battaglia, L. Ventimiglia, F. Vicari, A. Tamburini, A. Cipollina, G. Micale, Characterization of
3 Mg(OH)₂ powders produced from real saltworks bitterns at a pilot scale, *Powder Technology*, [Volume](#)
4 [443](#) (2024), 119918.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2024.119918>

5 **Characterization of Mg(OH)₂ powders produced from real saltworks** 6 **bitterns at a pilot scale**

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13 **ABSTRACT**

14 The growing demand for a reliable supply of minerals has pushed the European Union toward
15 seeking novel mineral sources. In the present work, the recovery of magnesium, in the form of
16 magnesium hydroxide, Mg(OH)₂, from saltworks bitterns was investigated at a pilot scale. The
17 natural bittern collected from Margi saltworks (Trapani, Italy) was treated with synthetic
18 sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solutions. The influence of different reactant concentrations, flow
19 rates and pH environments, on Mg(OH)₂ particle sizes, filtration characteristics, Mg²⁺
20 extraction performance and the Mg(OH)₂ solid purity was thoroughly assessed. The presence
21 of additional dissolved salts in NaOH solutions was also analysed. The pH environment was
22 found to be the most crucial parameter. On the one hand, high pH values ensured high Mg²⁺
23 recovery and powder purities, i.e. > 98 %, with boron content complying with market
24 requirements. On the other hand, filtration characteristics considerably worsened due to the
25 lyosorption phenomenon.

26 **KEYWORDS:** mineral recovery; magnesium hydroxide; pilot scale; critical raw material,
27 seawater mining.

28

29 **1. Introduction**

30 In the last years, there has been a growing interest in the concepts of ‘development minerals’,
31 ‘mineral security’ and ‘mineral poverty’. Franks et al. [1] have underlined the unambiguous
32 connection between the 17 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and the need for
33 minerals. However, the authors have marked that ‘mineral’, ‘mining’ or ‘miner’ terms were
34 surprisingly missing from the UN goals and targets.

35 The development of novel strategies for mineral recovery from unconventional sources and the
36 use of alternative manufacturing routes are therefore crucial to tackle today’s global challenges.

37 Almost 30 years ago, Turek and Gnot [2] have already investigated the possible production of
38 magnesium hydroxide compounds for the refractory industry by valorizing coal mine brines in
39 southern Poland. In the last decade, several research works have explored the potential of
40 concentrated salty solutions as alternative sources for mineral supply, e.g. seawater desalination
41 brines [3–5], saltworks bitterns [6] and Lithium/Magnesium rich brines [7,8].

42 Magnesium (Mg) is the eighth most abundant element on Earth and constitutes about 2% of the
43 Earth’s crust. It is the third major element dissolved in seawater [9]. Magnesium alloys are
44 extensively adopted in several industrial fields, e.g. electronics, aerospace or automotive [10],
45 owing to their properties, like low density and high mechanical properties. Magnesium
46 compounds such as magnesium hydroxide, $Mg(OH)_2$, magnesium carbonate, $MgCO_3$, and
47 magnesium oxide, MgO , are also extensively adopted in several industrial applications [9,11].

48 Magnesium has been listed among the 30 critical raw materials for the economic and social
49 development of the European Union due to its “mineral security” concern. As a matter of fact,
50 the EU imports more than 90 % of magnesium from China [12]. A promising alternative is the

51 recovery of magnesium from Mg^{2+} -containing saline solutions in the form of $Mg(OH)_2$ [13].
52 Synthesized $Mg(OH)_2$ solids can be either sold in the market or employed as an intermediate for
53 MgO or $MgCO_3$ production [14]. In the first case, $Mg(OH)_2$ powders must comply with market
54 requirements. For the synthesis of MgO refractory compounds, the equivalent boron and calcium
55 content in $Mg(OH)_2$ powders as boron oxide, B_2O_3 , and calcium oxide, CaO , must be below 0.07
56 % wt and 1 % wt, respectively [15]. For flame retard applications, $Mg(OH)_2$ powder purity must
57 be higher than 98.8 % and particle-specific surface area should be $< 15 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ [16]. For
58 pharmaceutical applications, powder purity and specific surface area must be $> 99 \%$ and >50
59 m^2/g , respectively. $Mg(OH)_2$ recovery from brines, however, is a challenging task and it requires
60 adequate operational strategies depending on the adopted feed solution and the desired final
61 product characteristics. Calcium and carbonate contents in seawater brines, in fact, may lead to
62 the co-precipitation of calcium compounds. Casas et al. [17] have implemented a pH fractionated
63 strategy for the precipitation of $Mg(OH)_2$ and $Ca(OH)_2$ by using $NaOH$ solutions at pH values of
64 10.8 and 12.8. A similar strategy has been also adopted by Vassallo et al. [18] at a pilot scale.
65 Many other alternatives for $Mg(OH)_2$ purity enhancement using also different alkaline solutions
66 can be found in the literature [3,19]. In this context, saltworks bitterns may represent promising
67 magnesium-containing resources. Saltworks are an ancient, yet consolidated route to recover
68 table salt from the sea. As by-products, bitterns are produced. Such streams are typically
69 considered as waste, while these can be further processed in order to extract additional minerals.
70 Since 2020, the European-funded SEArcularMINE project has been focusing its research
71 activities on the valorization of these waste solutions through the development of an innovative
72 integrated process for the recovery of critical raw materials such as magnesium. In the process,
73 reactants are going to be produced in loco, as for sodium hydroxide, via an Electrodialysis with
74 Bipolar Membrane (EDBM) unit. The advantage of adopting bitterns lies in their peculiar
75 composition. Bitterns are considerably concentrated in magnesium ions, reaching values up to

76 60 g/L, and, at the same time, are characterized by very low calcium concentrations, ~0.1 g/L.
77 The advantageous low calcium content is due to the fractionated evaporation process of seawater
78 that occurs in consecutive evaporation ponds where carbonates and calcium compounds
79 precipitate [20]. Notably, the average Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} concentrations in seawater are ~1.3 g/L and
80 ~0.4 g/L [4,21]. These values double, i.e. Mg^{2+} ~2.6 g/L and Ca^{2+} ~0.8 g/L, in seawater
81 desalination brines considering a water recovery of 50 % [4]. Even if the global seawater
82 desalination brine production is ~142 million m^3/day [22] which, considering a Mg^{2+}
83 concentration of 2.6 g/L and a density of the brines of $1050\text{ kg}/m^3$, can lead to a possible Mg^{2+}
84 availability of ~140,000 million tons/year, the very high calcium content in this brine often results
85 in a product with limited purity. In specific brines, Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} concentrations can be
86 significantly more concentrated than in seawater brines such as (i) in the Uyuni salar brine
87 (Bolivia, Mg^{2+} ~16 g/L and Ca^{2+} ~3 g/L [23]), (ii) in the Dead Sea (Mg^{2+} ~33 g/L and Ca^{2+} ~12
88 g/L [24]) or (iii) in bischofite brines (Mg^{2+} ~100 g/L and Ca^{2+} ~9 g/L [25]). The higher Mg^{2+} and
89 the lower Ca^{2+} content in bitterns are expected to favor the synthesis of highly pure Mg
90 compounds. Although bitterns are seasonal products, their global yearly production can be
91 estimated to be ~58 million tons. This value was calculated considering: (i) a global salt
92 production of ~276 million tons/year [26], (ii) a global salt production of ~27.6 million tons/year
93 (10 % of the total production) from saltworks, (iii) the production of 1.7 m^3 of residual bitterns
94 for 1 tons of salt and (iv) a density of bitterns of $1250\text{ kg}/m^3$. Consequently, the available Mg^{2+}
95 content in bitterns is ~2350 million tons/year, assuming an average Mg^{2+} concentration of 50 g/L.
96 This Mg^{2+} value is lower than 2 % of the amount that may be recovered from seawater
97 desalination brines. However, it should be noted that the global $Mg(OH)_2$ market is ~1.1 million
98 tons/year [27]. Based on the Mg^{2+} availability, ~5640 million tons/year and ~330,000 million
99 tons/year of $Mg(OH)_2$ could be produced from saltworks bitterns and seawater desalination
100 brines, respectively. Therefore, owing to the low Ca^{2+} concentration in saltworks bitterns, bitterns

101 represent an appealing resource for the production of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ compounds, complying with
102 market requirements, covering the total global $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ market demand. In our previous work,
103 the technical feasibility of Mg^{2+} recovery from saltworks bitterns and the purity degree of
104 synthesized $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ powders have been addressed at a laboratory scale [6].

105 The present work analyses several characteristics of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ suspensions and powders
106 synthesized from saltworks bitterns by adopting a pilot scale reactor for the possible scaled-up
107 production of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ compounds. A purposely developed $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ crystallizer, denominated
108 Magnesium Crystals-Granulometry-Controlled-Reactor prototype, was adopted. The Mg-CGCR
109 is an original design of ResourSEAs based on a multiple feed plug flow configuration concept
110 which has been also employed by Vassallo et al. [18], and whose different operating strategies
111 have been assessed by Morgante et al. [28]. The prototype was operated using synthetic NaOH
112 solutions treating a real bittern collected from the Margi evaporative ponds located in the district
113 of Trapani (Italy). $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ particle sizes, filtration characteristics, Mg^{2+} recovery and $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$
114 solid purity were investigated by varying: (i) reactants flow rates and concentrations; (ii) the final
115 suspension pH value, namely 10.8 and 12.8, and (iii) the addition of salts in NaOH solutions,
116 mimicking NaOH solutions produced in situ using the residual water after the SEArcularMINE
117 minerals extraction process. In the latter case, the aim was to investigate the influence of the
118 composition of a NaOH solution produced in loco by adopting a water recycle strategy after
119 magnesium, lithium [29] and trace elements (Cobalt, Gallium, etc.) [30] recovery. pH values
120 were chosen in order to determine whether the residual amount of Mg^{2+} in the filtrates could
121 comply with requirements for their possible adoption for the in loco production of NaOH
122 solutions through EDBM units [31]. As a matter of fact, EDBMs can be damaged if the
123 concentration of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions in the streams exceeds 10 ppm [32]. Moreover, the adoption
124 of the high pH value of 12.8 was aimed at investigating whether boron content in $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ solids
125 could be reduced below the threshold value required for refractory industry.

126 **2. Material and methods**

127 The production of Mg(OH)₂ solids from saltworks bitterns was carried out at the Brine
128 Excellent Centre at the Università degli Studi di Palermo by adopting the Mg-CGCR reactor.

129

130 **2.1 The Mg-CGCR prototype plant**

131 The Mg-CGCR pilot plant consisted of (i) a tank area, (ii) the Mg-CGCR crystallizer and (iii)
132 the piping and instrumentation system. Two 200 L tanks were employed to store the bittern
133 and the alkaline solution (NaOH), while two 500 L tanks contained the produced magnesium
134 hydroxide suspension and an extra fresh NaOH solution. A 125 L tank stored hydrochloric acid
135 or water for washing purposes. The reactor was a tubular reactor made of two coaxial regions.
136 Figure 1.a shows a picture of the Mg-CGCR reactor, while Figure 1.b is a schematic
137 representation of the Mg(OH)₂ precipitation process occurring inside it. The bittern solution
138 was fed in the inner region, while the NaOH solution was in the annular one [33]. The bittern
139 was injected into the alkaline compartment (i.e. annular region) through nozzles distributed
140 along the reactor length. The distributed injection of the bittern allowed a better
141 homogenization of the reagents all over the reactor volume, thus, improving the control of the
142 supersaturation (the driving force of a precipitation process). Specifically, in the reactor,
143 magnesium and hydroxide ions reacted leading to the precipitation of Mg(OH)₂:

145 In order to increase the performance of the reactor, part of the product was recycled back to the
146 inlet section and mixed with a fresh NaOH solution, before being fed into the annular region.

147 In our previous work, the adoption of a product recirculation strategy was found (i) to guarantee
148 an almost total recovery of Mg²⁺ from saline solutions, as well as (ii) to enhance the thickening
149 and filtration characteristics of the produced Mg(OH)₂ suspensions [28].

150

151 Figure 2 shows a simplified diagram of the pilot plant.
152 Three main hydraulic circuits can be identified: the brine (red colour), the soda (blue colour),
153 and the recirculation ones (black colour). All hydraulic systems (including pipes, valves and
154 fittings) were of polymeric materials, namely polypropylene (HPP, Polypropylene
155 homopolymer), Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) or High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE). Polymeric
156 materials were adopted because of their high chemical resistance to corrosive solutions, i.e.,
157 the bittern and the alkaline reagents. Bittern and soda solutions were pumped by P-1
158 (TEOREMA FG 204) and P-2 (Iwaki model MD30RZ), respectively. A three-way valve was
159 employed either to feed the NaOH solution directly to the reactor or to send it to the
160 recirculation circuit (N-3). Recirculation was carried out by splitting the outlet of the
161 crystallizer (N-1). The suspension, mixed with fresh NaOH solutions (N-2), was then pumped
162 by pump P-3 (Schmitt MPN 130). All the electronic components were connected to an external
163 Data Acquisition Board (National Instruments model NI 9481, NI 9203, NI 9264, NI 9265). A
164 monitoring and control software was implemented in Labview® environment. Two KRONHE
165 model OPTIFLUX 4300 C flow meters were installed in each hydraulic circuit of the reactants
166 and a KRONHE model OPTIFLUX 4100 was located in the recirculation loop. Suspensions
167 pH was monitored by a pH meter (Krohne PH8320) placed at the outlet section of the Mg-
168 CGCR reactor. All the experimental tests were conducted by adopting the recirculation
169 strategy.

170

171 **2.2 Characteristics of the employed solutions**

172 A bittern collected from Margi saltwork (Trapani, Italy) was employed in the experimental
173 campaign. Table 1 lists the concentration of the macro and micro components identified in the
174 bittern. Macro components were detected using Ion Chromatography (IC, Metrohm model 882
175 compact IC plus), while calcium and boron were measured by flame-atomic absorption
176 spectroscopy (F-AAS) and Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-

177 OES, PerkinElmer Optima 2100 DV) techniques, respectively. The bittern was diluted into
178 ultrapure water before analysis.

179

180 **Table 1** Concentrations of the macro and micro components in the Margi bittern. Analytical
181 techniques adopted for concentration assessment are also indicated, namely Ion
182 Chromatography (IC), Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES)
183 and flame-atomic absorption spectroscopy (F-AAS).

Macro Components	Conc. [g/L]	Analytical technique
Na ⁺	54±2	IC
K ⁺	13±1	IC
Mg ²⁺	49±1	IC
Cl ⁻	183±5	IC
SO ₄ ²⁻	61±2	IC
Br ⁻	2.3±0.3	IC
Micro Components	Conc. [mg/L]	Analytical technique
B	123±6	ICP-OES
Ca	134±5	F-AAS

184

185 Mg²⁺ concentration was ~49 g/l, while B and Ca were ~123 and ~134 mg/L, respectively.

186 Bittern solutions were employed without any pre-treatment, such as decolorization. NaOH
187 alkaline solutions were prepared by filling the soda tank with softened water and dissolving
188 sodium hydroxide pellets (Inovyn, purity grade>99%). NaOH 0.50 M and 1.00 M solutions
189 were targeted. In some tests, other salts were dissolved to mimic a possible NaOH-rich solution
190 produced by an Electrodialysis with Bipolar Membrane unit, in the following defined as doped
191 NaOH solutions. In these cases, sodium chloride (Volterra; purity >99.9%), potassium chloride
192 (Toro) and sodium sulphate (Crimidesa; purity >99.6%) salts were added with a final
193 concentration of 2.52 M, 0.54 M and 0.32 M, respectively. NaOH solution concentrations were
194 assessed by titration.

195

196

197 **2.3 Experimental cases**

198 The influence of (i) reactant flow rates and concentrations, (ii) the final suspension pH value
 199 and (iii) the addition of salts in the NaOH solutions on (i) Mg(OH)₂ particle sizes and filtration
 200 characteristics, (ii) Mg²⁺ recovery and (iii) Mg(OH)₂ solid purity was investigated. Table 2 lists
 201 the details of all the investigated cases. Mg(OH)₂ suspensions were produced at two final steady
 202 state pH values of 10.8 and 12.8, i.e. the stoichiometric reaction pH value, 10.8 [18], and a
 203 considerable high hydroxide ion excess operating condition, 12.8. To achieve these pH values,
 204 the NaOH solution flow rate was increased keeping the bittern solution one constant.

205

206 *Table 2 Concentrations and flow rates of the bittern and NaOH solutions adopted in the*
 207 *experimental campaign. Final measured Mg(OH)₂ suspension pH values are also reported.*
 208 *The letter D indicates the use of a doped NaOH solution (addition of 2.52 M NaCl, 0.54 M KCl*
 209 *and 0.32 M Na₂SO₄). All tests were performed at a recirculation flow rate of 1200±50 L/h.*

Cases	Bittern Mg ²⁺ concentration [M]	Bittern Flow rate [L/h]	NaOH concentration [M]	NaOH flow rate [L/h]	Final suspension pH [-]
#1a	2.02±0.04	12±0.5	1.00±0.02	47±1	10.8±0.1
#1b	2.02±0.04	12±0.5	1.00±0.02	94±1	12.8±0.3
#2a	1.00±0.02	12±0.5	1.00±0.02	25±0.5	10.8±0.1
#2b	1.00±0.02	12±0.5	1.00±0.02	49±1	12.8±0.3
#3a	2.02±0.04	12±0.5	0.50±0.01	96±1	10.8±0.1
#3b	2.02±0.04	12±0.5	0.50±0.01	155±1	12.8±0.3
#4a	2.02±0.04	30±0.5	0.50±0.01	235±2	10.8±0.1
#4b	2.02±0.04	30±0.5	0.50±0.01	338±3	12.8±0.3
#5a	2.02±0.04	30±0.5	0.50±0.01 D	230±2	10.8±0.1
#5b	2.02±0.04	30±0.5	0.50±0.01 D	345±3	12.8±0.3

210

211 Cases #1 (Mg²⁺ concentration of 2.02 M) and #2 (Mg²⁺ concentration of 1.00 M) investigated
 212 the influence of the bittern concentration. In Cases #2, 20 L of the Margi bittern were added to
 213 20 L of softened water for bittern dilution. Cases #3 were performed using a 0.50 M NaOH
 214 solution, keeping the same bittern composition and flow rate as those of Cases #1, namely 12
 215 L/h and a Mg²⁺ concentration of 2.02 M. In Cases #4, the bittern flow rate was increased up to

216 30 L/h, while all the other parameters were as those of Cases #3. Cases #5 had the same
217 characteristics of Cases #4, but a doped NaOH solution was employed.

218

219 **2.4 Experimental procedure and analytical techniques**

220 Hydraulic leakage tests were performed before each experiment. Mg(OH)₂ suspensions were
221 collected at the outlet line of the reactor for each test and pH value, namely 10.8 and 12.8.
222 Figure 3 illustrates the post-treatment procedure of the collected suspensions. Note that,
223 although a pilot scale reactor was adopted, a laboratory procedure was followed for the
224 Mg(OH)₂ post-treatment and analyses.

225 Two 100 mL graduated glass cylinders were filled with fresh Mg(OH)₂ suspensions. The
226 suspension thickened for ~48 hours: step 1.a in Figure 3. Other 100 mL of the suspension was
227 employed for particle size distribution (PSD) analysis, step 1.b in Figure 3. The Malvern
228 Mastersizer 2000 laser granulometer was used following the same procedure reported in
229 Battaglia et al. [34]. PSDs were measured before and after applying an ultrasound treatment
230 and adding the poly(acrylic acid), PAA, adopted as an anti-agglomerant agent.

231 After thickening, from step 1.a, suspensions were re-suspended in the cylinder and filtered.
232 Filtrations were carried out in a Buchner funnel using 1.6 μm fiberglass filters (Whatman GF/A
233 grade, GE Healthcare Life Sciences) of 70 mm diameter at an operating pressure of 0.5 bar. A
234 vacuum pump (BUCHI, VACUUM V700) was employed along with a regulation valve and a
235 pressure gauge: step 2 in Figure 3. Each suspension in the cylinder was filtered separately. 40
236 mL of filtered solutions was targeted. The filtration time was recorded for each test. The cake
237 permeability coefficient, θ_{perm} , was then calculated as reported in Morgante et al. [28]:

$$238 \quad \theta_{perm} = \frac{V_{sol}}{t_{filt} \cdot A_{filter} \cdot P_{filt.}} \cdot \left(\frac{V_{sol} \cdot m_{Mg(OH)_2}}{\rho_{cake} \cdot A_{filter}} \right) \quad (2)$$

239 where V_{sol} is the volume of solution permeated during the filtration [m³], $m_{Mg(OH)_2}$ is the magma
240 density of the slurry [g/L], ρ_{cake} is the density of the cake, assumed to be that of the water

241 [kg/m³], A_{filter} is the surface area of the filter [m²], $t_{filt.}$ is the time required for filtration [min],
242 and $P_{filt.}$ is the filtration operating pressure [bar].

243 The Mg(OH)₂ cake was then washed with demineralized water until the conductivity of the
244 filtered water was lower than 200 μS/cm. The cake was dried in an oven at 120 °C for 24h:
245 step 3 in Figure 3. It was then milled, and powders were kept for additional 24 h in the oven at
246 180 °C to further reduce their humidity content (intermediate step between 3 and 4, not reported
247 in Figure 3).

248 Mg(OH)₂ powder purity was assessed through several techniques: step 4 in Figure 3. The Mg²⁺
249 content in Mg(OH)₂ powder was analyzed by Ion chromatography (IC) analyses (Metrohm
250 model 882 compact IC plus). 150 mg of Mg(OH)₂ powder were dissolved in 1.00 M
251 hydrochloric acid (Honeywell-Fluka;>30% for trace analysis). The cationic purity was
252 calculated as follows:

$$253 \quad \text{Cation purity} = \frac{Mg_{IC}^{2+}}{\sum_{i=1}^N c_i} \quad (3)$$

254 where Mg_{IC}^{2+} is the Mg²⁺ concentration in the samples, c_i is the concentration of the generic i -
255 the cation specie and N is the number of total cations detected by the IC.

256 Powder mass purity was determined by thermogravimetric analysis (TG or TGA). TGA
257 analyses were conducted at a heating rate of 10 °C/min from 30 °C to 1000 °C with a constant
258 nitrogen flow of 20 mL/min. Analyses were conducted by adopting the STA 449 F1 Jupiter
259 analyzer, NETZSCH. Mass purity was estimated as the ratio between the mass loss detected
260 between 320 °C and 800 °C ($\Delta m_{320-800^\circ C}$) and the theoretical Mg(OH)₂ mass loss
261 ($\Delta m_{theoretical}$, 30.8 % wt [35]):

$$262 \quad \text{Mass Purity} = \frac{\Delta m_{320-800^\circ C}}{\Delta m_{theoretical}} \quad (4)$$

263 The Mg(OH)₂ decomposition into MgO occurs in the temperature range between 320 °C and
264 480 °C, however, many authors have attributed the mass loss occurring from 480 °C to 800 °C

265 to the slow OH⁻ groups release from the MgO lattice [6,36,37]. The description of a typical
266 Mg(OH)₂ thermogravimetric plot is reported in the Appendix A. Mg(OH)₂ powder purity was
267 also analyzed by X-ray diffraction, XRD, technique using CuKα radiation (1.542° Å, 40 KV,
268 100 mA) in the 2θ range of 10–70° at a step size of 1°/min. The RIGAKU model D.MAX 2500
269 HK was used. Boron concentration in the powders was quantified by Inductively Coupled
270 Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES). 100 mg of Mg(OH)₂ powder were
271 dissolved in 50 ml of a 2 wt% nitric acid solution (Chem-lab; 70%; HNO₃ ultrapure). The
272 analysis was conducted by adopting the PerkinElmer Optima 2100 DV spectrometer. The
273 morphology of the Mg(OH)₂ powders was also assessed by Scanning Electron Microscopy
274 (SEM) technique using the Scanning Electron Microscope FEI Quanta 200 FEG. A gold
275 coating was applied to make samples conductive, step 5 in Figure 3
276 Mg²⁺ recovery was evaluated by Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) complexometric
277 titration of the filtered solutions (before cake washing step): step 6 in Figure 3. The recovery
278 was then calculated as follows:

$$279 \quad Mg^{2+} recovery = \frac{(Mg_{BITTERN}^{2+}/DF) - Mg_{Filtered}^{2+}}{(Mg_{BITTERN}^{2+}/DF)} \quad (5)$$

280 where $Mg_{BITTERN}^{2+}$ and $Mg_{Filtered}^{2+}$ are the Mg²⁺ concentration in the initial bittern and in the
281 filtered solutions. *DF* is the dilution factor that considers the mixing phenomenon between the
282 bittern and the NaOH aqueous solutions, namely the ratio between the sum of the bittern and
283 NaOH flow rates with respect to the bittern one.

284

285 **3. Results and discussion**

286 In the following section, the characterization of Mg(OH)₂ particles produced by the Mg-CGCR
287 reactor is discussed. The terms “agglomerates” and “aggregates” are used to distinguish among
288 different particle assembly states. Specifically, aggregates are assemblies of primary particles
289 composed of crystallites joined together by strong chemical bonds; while agglomerates are

290 made of more or less loose arrangements of primary particles, aggregates or a mixture of the
291 two kept together by crystalline bridges or electrostatic forces. Agglomerate structures can be
292 broken down by physical treatment such as sonication.

293

294 **3.1. Mg(OH)₂ particle size distributions**

295 Figure 4 shows particle size distributions (PSDs) of Mg(OH)₂ particles synthesized in all five
296 tests before and after the ultrasound and PAA treatment.

297 Before PAA and ultrasound treatment, particles ranged from 1 to 10 μm in Mg(OH)₂
298 suspensions characterized by a final pH value of 10.8, Cases #a, regardless of the operating
299 conditions or the reagent concentrations. This behavior is most likely due to the product
300 recycling strategy that favors aggregation phenomena between particles. As a matter of fact,
301 the injection of fresh reagents in a suspension of Mg(OH)₂ particles enhances the aggregation
302 of the particles rather than their growth. This is caused by the extremely fast precipitation
303 process of Mg(OH)₂ particles that leads to supersaturation levels far from the metastable zone
304 [38]. Conversely, bigger particles were measured in suspensions characterized by a final pH of
305 12.8, Cases #b. Mg(OH)₂ particles precipitated into a high pH environment have a high
306 tendency to adsorb the surrounding liquid phase. This phenomenon is known as lyosorption
307 that leads to the formation of lyspheres. Lyspheres close to each other create agglomerates
308 characterized by internal pores containing mother liquor [2]. Under this condition, the size of
309 the agglomerates can depend on the local supersaturation level and the specific operating
310 conditions. Case #1b was characterized by the highest local supersaturation due to the use of
311 the most concentrated reagents, namely Mg²⁺ and OH⁻ of 2.02 M and 1.00 M, respectively. The
312 high supersaturation level can lead to strong aggregates that can agglomerate producing big
313 particles. Cases #4b and #5b had a higher bittern flow rate with respect to Cases #2b and #3b,
314 inducing stronger local jets of the bittern solution in the alkaline compartment (higher local

315 mixing conditions) favoring the agglomeration tendency of the particles [34]. In Case #5b, the
316 addition of salts in the NaOH solution increased the ionic strength of the solution affecting the
317 agglomeration phenomena. PSDs of Cases #2b and #3b were similar to those of Cases #a,
318 although tails toward bigger particles can be observed due to particle agglomeration.
319 After PAA and ultrasound treatment, the assembly state of particles was well determined. PSDs
320 still ranged between 1 and 10 μm , in suspensions produced at a final pH value of 10.8,
321 indicating that particles were aggregates. Conversely, smaller particles were detected in
322 suspensions characterized by a final pH value of 12.8 due to the lyosorption phenomenon.
323 Case #1b showed a bimodal distribution with mean peaks centred around 0.2 and 8 μm . The
324 presence of big particles can be related to the highest supersaturation level in the reactor, as
325 discussed above. Cases #4 and #5 showed the presence of some big particles, while Cases #3
326 and #2 were characterized mainly by particles ranging from 0.08 to 1 μm . Interestingly,
327 nanoparticles were not reported by Morgante et al. [28] when using the recycling strategy.
328 However, the authors performed tests at a maximum pH value of 12, thus the here adopted
329 higher pH value most likely induced a more pronounced lyosorption phenomenon.

330

331 **3.2 Filtration characteristics**

332 $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ suspension magma density values, filtration times and cake filtration permeability
333 values, Eq. (2), are reported in Table 3.

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338 **Table 3** Magma density values, filtration times required to collect 40 mL of solution and cake
 339 filtration permeability values evaluated for all the investigated cases.

Cases	Magma density [g/L]	Time (min)	θ [-]
#1a	24.2	2.3±0.3	2.8E-06
#1b	13.5	11.1±0.6	2.6E-07
#2a	19.3	0.7±0.1	6.0E-06
#2b	11.7	7.0±0.4	3.4E-07
#3a	13.2	2.0±0.2	1.5E-06
#3b	8.5	7.2±0.9	3.0E-07
#4a	13.5	3.0±0.1	9.9E-07
#4b	9.7	7.5±0.2	2.8E-07
#5a	13.7	6.9±0.7	4.3E-07
#5b	9.5	13.0±1.8	1.6E-07

340
 341 Filtration times varied between ~1 and ~3 minutes in Cases #a, while only Case #5a required
 342 a filtration time of ~7 minutes. The latter longer time was probably caused by the higher ionic
 343 strength of the solution due to the added salts and the local mixing conditions. As for Case #5,
 344 in fact, also Case #4a required more time than Cases #1a, #2a and #3a, probably due to the
 345 higher mixing regimes in the reactor induced by the strong jets caused by the higher bittern
 346 flow rate. Case #1a required more time than Cases #2a and #3a probably due to the higher local
 347 supersaturation attained in the reactor induced by the use of the most concentrated reagents. It
 348 can be also observed that magma density was also the highest among all the analysed cases.
 349 Case #2a was found to be the fastest probably due to the use of the lowest NaOH flow rates
 350 that can reduce mixing phenomena in the reactor. Case #3a required more time than Case#2a
 351 although it was characterized by a lower supersaturation level in the reactor, but higher NaOH
 352 flow rates were employed affecting mixing conditions. Overall, it should be noted that, except
 353 for Case #5a, filtration times are quite close to each other, indicating that the operating
 354 conditions did not have a strong influence on the filtration process most likely due to the
 355 adoption of the product recycling strategy [28].

356 Filtration times were greater in Cases #b ranging from ~6 to ~13 minutes. Longer times can be
357 related to the presence of smaller particles as shown by PSDs in accordance with the well-
358 known difficulties in filtration of Mg(OH)₂ particles produced at high pH values [2]. Case #5b
359 reported the highest filtration time confirming the negative impact of the high ionic strength on
360 the filtration process of Mg(OH)₂ powders. Again, the operating conditions did not significantly
361 affected filtration times. Only Case #1b reported a greater filtration time than Cases #2b, #3b
362 and #4b probably due to a negative influence of the co-presence of small and big particles, see
363 Figure 4, precipitated at the highest supersaturation level attained in the reactor. Cake filtration
364 permeability values were in accordance with those reported by Morgante et al. [28]. Case #2a
365 had the highest θ value, while Case #5b was characterized by the lowest one.

366 For the sake of completeness, SEM observations of Mg(OH)₂ powders synthesized in Case #1a
367 are shown in Figure 5.

368 Nanometric Mg(OH)₂ globular particles can be observed. The globular shape can be attributed
369 to the high local supersaturation levels attained in the reactor due to the direct mixing of NaOH
370 and bittern solutions through the nozzles. As discussed by Romano et al. [39], high local
371 supersaturation levels do not favor the growth of hexagonal Mg(OH)₂ crystals, leading to
372 nanometric globular particles. The observed morphology suggests that the specific surface area
373 of the particles is most likely higher than 50 m²/g, as reported in the literature [39–42]. The
374 morphology and the expected specific surface area of the synthesized Mg(OH)₂ particles thus
375 indicate that particles are not suitable for flame retardant application requiring further treatment,
376 such as the hydrothermal treatment [40], although they could be of interest for pharmaceutical
377 applications. Similar SEM images were obtained by analysing the other Mg(OH)₂ particles,
378 thus here omitted for the sake of brevity. Unfortunately, the aggregation level between particles
379 could not be distinguished among the different samples.

380

381 **3.3 Mg²⁺ recovery**

382 The Mg²⁺ content in the filtered solutions after solid hydroxide separation was analyzed by
383 EDTA. Figure 6 shows the Mg²⁺ concentration measured in the filtrates (bars) along with the
384 evaluated Mg²⁺ recovery (diamonds symbols) by Eq. (5).

385 Mg²⁺ ions in the filtrates were at least two orders of magnitude lower than in the feed solution,
386 being mostly lower than 50 mg/L (Mg²⁺ recovery higher than 99 %). A clear difference was
387 observed between Cases #a (final pH 10.8) and #b (final pH 12.8). All Cases #b were
388 characterized by lower Mg²⁺ content due to the higher final Mg(OH)₂ suspensions pH value of
389 12.8 that ensures all Mg²⁺ reacted with hydroxide ions (residual Mg²⁺ ions <10 mg/L), as also
390 reported in the literature [43]. Only Cases #4a and #5a (bittern flow rate of 30 L/min) were
391 characterized by Mg²⁺ concentrations of ~300 mg/L with a recovery of ~94 %. In both Cases,
392 a recovery higher than 99 % was attained by increasing the final suspension pH to 12.8 (Cases
393 #b). Overall, neither (i) reactants flow rates and concentrations nor (ii) the addition of salts in
394 the NaOH solutions, considerably influenced the Mg²⁺ recovery, which resulted to be mainly
395 affected by the reaction pH environment. This can be attributed to the instantaneous nature of
396 the Mg(OH)₂ reaction that consumes all Mg²⁺ and hydroxide ions as soon as they meet. Results
397 also clearly provide indications about the possible use of the filtrates for the in loco production
398 of NaOH solutions through EDBM units. Specifically, only Cases #b allowed Mg²⁺
399 concentrations lower or slightly above 10 ppm to be achieved, which is the threshold
400 concentration that does not damage EDBM units [32].

401

402 **3.4 Mg(OH)₂ purity**

403 **3.4.1 Mg(OH)₂ cationic purity**

404 Mg(OH)₂ powder cationic purity was assessed by IC analysis. Figure 7 shows the cation
405 percentage in Mg(OH)₂ solids detected for Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺ and Na⁺ species. Ca²⁺ and Na⁺

406 concentrations values were always lower than their Limit Of Quantification (LOQ), namely
407 1.3 mg/g and 5 mg/g, respectively. Cationic purity (Mg^{2+} percentage) was calculated using Eq.
408 (3) and considering the LOQ values for Ca^{2+} and Na^+ species. Thus, Ca^{2+} and Na^+ concentration
409 reported in Figure 7 can be either attributed to a limit of the analytical apparatus or to an actual
410 low ionic concentration. Na^+ may potentially be present in the final product as a result from a
411 non-ideal cake washing step. Finally, the minor presence of Ca^{2+} can be related to co-
412 precipitation of calcium species in the reactor.

413 Mg^{2+} cation percentage, i.e. the cationic purity, was always higher than 98.4 % independently
414 of the operating conditions, indicating highly pure compounds. It must be stressed that, cationic
415 purity values are underestimated since LOQ values for calcium and sodium cations were
416 considered in Eq. (3). Interestingly, cationic purity is high also in Cases #5 (doped NaOH
417 solution), suggesting a negligible influence of the presence of additional dissolved salts in the
418 NaOH solution. The high purity achieved is in accordance with literature data on the synthesis
419 of $Mg(OH)_2$ compounds from Mg^{2+} -containing solutions with low calcium or carbonate content
420 precipitated adopting NaOH solutions [3]. In this case, the use of the bittern ensured the high
421 purity of the particles. As a matter of fact, bittern had a Ca^{2+} concentration almost 1000 times
422 lower than the Mg^{2+} one, see **Table 1**, preventing the precipitation of contaminants species such
423 as calcium carbonate, calcium sulphate or calcium hydroxide, as discussed in the introduction
424 section. This reduced the negative impact of the presence of Ca^{2+} on $Mg(OH)_2$ particle purity.
425 Adopting an industrial perspective, this last finding indicates the possibility to maximize in-
426 situ water reuse to produce NaOH solution containing NaCl and Na_2SO_4 impurities.
427 Moreover, based on Ca^{2+} concentration (LOQ values), the equivalent CaO content in the
428 $Mg(OH)_2$ powder was always lower than 1 %. This result marked the interest in the synthesized
429 $Mg(OH)_2$ powders as a precursor for the MgO refractory industry [15].

430
431

432 **3.4.2 Mg(OH)₂ mass purity**

433 Mg(OH)₂ mass purities evaluated using Eq. (4) are reported in Figure 8.

434 Mass purity values were always higher than 98 %. Once again the high amount of Mg²⁺ in the
435 bittern and the low Ca²⁺ content guaranteed the high purity of the powders. The highest values
436 were attained in solids produced from Mg(OH)₂ suspensions characterized by a final pH of
437 12.8 (Cases #b). This was attributed to less boron adsorption on Mg(OH)₂ surface at high pH
438 values [19]. Only Case #5b showed a value lower than that of Case #5a, probably due to the
439 use of the doped NaOH solution and its effect at high pH values.

440 Figure 9 shows the boron content in Mg(OH)₂ solids.

441 Boron concentration was found to be one order of magnitude lower in Mg(OH)₂ solids
442 produced from suspensions characterized by a final pH value of 12.8, i.e. Cases #b, with respect
443 to those having a final pH value of 10.8, namely Cases #a. Specifically, boron concentrations
444 were lower than ~0.15 mg/g in Cases #b, while they were ~1 mg/g in Cases #a. The lower
445 boron concentration in samples synthesized in Cases #b was expected. The pH of the reaction
446 environment, in fact, affects the boron adsorption on Mg(OH)₂ surfaces. The boron adsorption
447 occurs by the interaction B(OH)₄⁻ ions and the OH⁻ groups of Mg(OH)₂ compounds [44]. At
448 low pH values, Mg(OH)₂ particles are characterized by a positive charge, while above the
449 isoelectric point, i.e. pH 12 [34], particles are negative. The different charge of the particles
450 favors the B(OH)₄⁻ ions adsorption below the isoelectric point, while it hinders the adsorption
451 above it. From an industrial perspective, the maximum B content in Mg(OH)₂ powders for
452 refractory applications must be ~0.11 mg-B/g-Mg(OH)₂ [15]. Notably, the boron content
453 evaluated in Cases #2b and #3b reached this threshold value, while it was only slightly above,
454 i.e. less than 0.04 ppm, in the other Cases #b. This result highlights the need of a considerable
455 NaOH excess to reduce the boron content in Mg(OH)₂ solids. In our previous study, in fact, the
456 boron content in powders synthesized at pH values of about 12.2 from real bitters was ~0.3

457 mg-B/g-Mg(OH)₂ [6]. An alternative strategy for boron content reduction without the use of
458 excessive NaOH solutions would be a bittern pre-treatment such as a boron adsorption stage
459 through ions exchange resins [45,46].

460 Note that, values refer to measured concentrations of boron element from ICP-OES analyses,
461 rather than a specific boron compound, as boric acid, B(OH)₃, which is the typical boron
462 species that exists in seawater.

463

464 **3.4.3 Crystal structure**

465 The purity of synthesized Mg(OH)₂ powders was also qualitatively assessed by XRD analysis.

466 The XRD pattern of Case #1a is reported Figure 10.

467 XRD pattern confirmed the high purity of the synthesized Mg(OH)₂ particles. Only typical
468 diffraction peaks of the brucite crystalline form of Mg(OH)₂ (JCPDS 7-239) were detected. No
469 extra peaks from impurities were observed. Similar XRD patterns were obtained for the other
470 Cases and are here omitted for the sake of brevity.

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482 **Conclusions**

483 Saltworks bitterns are by-products of sea salt production from seawater in saltworks. Bitterns
484 are highly concentrated solutions in critical minerals such as magnesium. In the present work,
485 $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ powders produced from saltworks bitterns by adopting a pilot scale reactor were
486 characterized. The bittern collected from the Margi saltwork located in the district of Trapani,
487 Italy, was treated with synthetic NaOH solutions. A purposely designed crystallizer, the
488 Magnesium Crystals-Granulometry-Controlled-Reactor prototype, the Mg-CGCR, was
489 employed.

490 $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ powders were produced under several operating conditions that, except for the
491 reaction pH environment and solution ionic strength, did not considerably affect particle size
492 distributions, filtration times, Mg^{2+} recovery and the purity of synthesized $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ powder.

493 $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ particles ranged always between 1 and 10 μm in suspensions characterized by a final
494 pH value of 10.8 regardless of the operating conditions or the use of ultrasounds, demonstrating
495 the production of strong aggregates. Conversely, the high pH environment attained at the pH
496 value of 12.8 favored the lyosorption phenomenon producing smaller particles, namely
497 between 0.08 and 1 μm , prone to form big agglomerates. The pH environment influenced
498 filtration times of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ particles. Particles produced at pH values of 10.8 were up to 6
499 times easier to filter than those produced at the pH value of 12.8, due to the lyosorption
500 phenomenon. Nanometric globular shaped particles were reported in all cases due to the direct
501 mixing between the adopted reagents. This morphology could be of interest for pharmaceutical
502 applications, while it would require further treatment for the flame retard field.

503 The Mg^{2+} recovery > 99 % was achieved when the final pH of the produced $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ slurries
504 was ~12.8, with a final Mg^{2+} concentration of about ~10 ppm complying with requirements for
505 the use of filtered solutions for the in loco production of chemicals by membrane-based units.
506 $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ powder cationic and mass purity were always >98.4 % and >98 %, respectively. The

507 equivalent CaO in the powder was <1 wt %, while the boron content was lower than <0.07 %
508 only in Mg(OH)₂ powders synthesized at pH values of 12.8, making the powder suitable to
509 produce MgO refractory grade. In all cases, XRD patterns showed only characteristic peaks of
510 Mg(OH)₂ compounds, thus indicating the high purity of the synthesized powders. The addition
511 of dissolved salts (NaCl, Na₂SO₄ and KCl) in the NaOH solutions slightly affected the
512 Mg(OH)₂ powder purity, while it had a strong influence on filtration characteristics reporting
513 the longest filtration times. In these cases, the mass purity was the lowest, although still above
514 98 %. The present experimental campaign marks the high potential of saltworks bitterns as a
515 promising alternative for the worldwide “mineral security” supply of Mg(OH) compounds. The
516 study also highlights the critical aspects to be considered for the recovery of this compound
517 from Mg²⁺-containing solutions, as also seawater brines. An accurate choice of the pH
518 environment is mandatory. On the one hand, high pH reaction environments are required to
519 reduce as much as possible the Mg²⁺ content in filtered solutions as well as to reduce the boron
520 content in Mg(OH)₂ particles. On the other hand, high pH environments cause lyosorption
521 phenomenon and particle filtration difficulties. In addition, the direct contact between reagents
522 should be avoided if hexagonal shaped Mg(OH)₂ particles would be obtained due to the high
523 local supersaturation levels attained in the reactor. These findings can be also considered for
524 the production of Mg(OH)₂ compounds.

525

526 **Acknowledgments**

527 This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and
528 innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 869467 (SEArcularMINE). This output
529 reflects only the author’s view. The European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA)
530 and the European Commission cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the
531 information contained therein.

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544

545

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Figures

698 **Figure 1**

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701 **Figure 2**

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706 **Figure 3**

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710 **Figure 4**

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723 **Figure 6**

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728 **Figure 7**

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731 **Figure 8**

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739 **Figure 9**

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743 **Figure 10**

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Captions

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748 **Figure 1** A picture of the Mg-CGCR prototype (a). A schematic representation of the Mg(OH)₂
749 precipitation process in the reactor (b).

750

751 **Figure 2** Simplified diagram of the Mg-CGCR pilot plant.

752

753 **Figure 3** Post-treatment procedure of Mg(OH)₂ suspensions produced by adopting the Mg-
754 CGCR prototype: (1.a) suspension thickening; (1.b) particle size distribution assessment; (2)
755 suspension filtration; (3) cake drying; (4) Mg(OH)₂ powder purity analysis by
756 thermogravimetric (TGA), Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-
757 OES), Ion chromatography (IC) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) techniques; (5) Mg(OH)₂
758 morphology by Scanning Electron Microscopy technique; (6) Mg²⁺ content assessment in the
759 filtrates through Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) titration.

760

761 **Figure 4** PSDs of synthesized Mg(OH)₂ particles before (on the left) and after (on the right)
762 ultrasound treatment and the addition of PAA. Cases #a are straight lines, while Cases #1b,
763 #2b, #3b, #4b and #5b are dotted, fine dashed, coarse dashed, dashed-pointed and coarse-fine
764 dashed lines, respectively.

765

766 **Figure 5** A SEM image of the Mg(OH)₂ particles synthesized in Case #1a taken at a
767 magnification of 40,000 x.

768

769 **Figure 6** Mg²⁺ concentration in filtrates assessed by EDTA (solid or scattered coloured bars)
770 and corresponding Mg²⁺ recovery values (diamonds).

771

772 **Figure 7** *Mg(OH)₂ cationic purity. Ca²⁺ and Na⁺ traces detected in the samples were always*
773 *lower than their Limit Of Quantification, namely 5 mg/g and 1.3 mg/g for Na⁺ and Ca²⁺,*
774 *respectively.*

775

776 **Figure 8** *Magnesium hydroxide mass purity values, Eq. (4), evaluated by TG analysis.*

777

778 **Figure 9** *Boron content in Mg(OH)₂ powders synthesized by adopting the Mg-CGCR. Results*
779 *were collected by ICP-OES measurements.*

780

781 **Figure 10** *XRD pattern of Mg(OH)₂ powder synthesized in Case #1a.*

782

783

784 **Appendix A: Mg(OH)₂ thermogravimetric curves**

785 Thermogravimetric (TG) analysis provides information about a sample mass evolution as a
786 function of temperature or time. The analysis is carried out under a controlled atmosphere and
787 by adopting a controlled temperature program. TG curves and their derivate with respect to
788 temperature (DTG) are the outcomes of the analysis. The TG curve reports the mass evolution
789 of a sample as a function of temperature, while DTG one shows the rate of change of mass with
790 respect to temperature against temperature. Downward and upward DTG curves indicate
791 endothermic and exothermic phenomena, respectively. Figure A 1 shows a typical TG-DTG
792 plot obtained by analyzing the Mg(OH)₂ powders produced by the Mg-CGCR prototype.
793 Specifically, curves refer to Case #3a, see Table 2.

794

795

796 **Figure A 1** Thermogravimetric analysis of Case #3a.

797

798 As discussed and explained in Battaglia et al. [6], three main weight losses can be observed:

- 799 1) A first mass loss between 30°C and 320°C. It is related to the release of residual moisture,
800 free water, or adsorbed water in the sample. Water of crystallization can be also lost from
801 hydrated compounds. Often, this mass loss is attributed to sample humidity.

802 2) The second major mass loss occurs between 320 °C and 480 °C. In this temperature range,
803 the Mg(OH)₂ compound degrades to MgO releasing water. For Case #3a, the mass loss is
804 ~27.7%, which is significantly lower than the expected theoretical one, namely 30.8%.

805 3) A significant further mass loss of ~2.6 % is detected in the temperature range between 480
806 °C and 800 °C. This mass loss is attributed to the slow and continuous desorption of residual
807 OH⁻ groups bound to the MgO lattice produced from the Mg(OH)₂ degradation [36,37]. In
808 addition, it is worth noting that, the DTG curve does not show the presence of any peak in
809 this temperature range, thus suggesting that no other processes are occurring (no other
810 hydroxides or carbonates degradation). Therefore, this mass loss was considered for
811 Mg(OH)₂ mass purity estimation, Eq.(4). In Figure A 1, the total Mg(OH)₂ mass loss (from
812 320°C to 800°C) is 30.3 %, considerably closer to the theoretical one.

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